

Pattern and structural detection in grayscale images through the application of quantile graphs in higher-dimensional spaces

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ABSTRACT

Deep Learning and Machine Learning algorithms effectively handle and categorize various data formats, such as time series, text, and images, thereby tackling difficulties in both supervised and unsupervised learning. The practical applications of certain algorithms, especially convolutional neural networks (CNNs), are limited by the requirement for extensive datasets, substantial training, and intricate parameter adjustments, which frequently involve trial and error. Recent research has attempted to provide alternative solutions for feature extraction and classification to overcome these limitations. Quantile graphs (QGs), which were initially applied to time series, transform data points into a complex network of quantiles, thereby identifying key structural patterns with minimal computational requirements. These graphs have yielded promising results in the analysis of physiological time series linked to brain function and disorders, such as Alzheimer's disease. This investigation expands quantile graphs to identify images and introduces a method for extracting features that can be used by machine learning/deep learning (ML/DL) in the field of computer vision. This study employed two widely recognized benchmark datasets: the Modified National Institute of Standards and Technology (MNIST) handwritten digit database and Fashion MNIST. The performance of the proposed QGs was compared with that of CNNs. Our results indicate that although CNNs exhibit better accuracy in certain instances, the proposed QGs surpass CNNs in other situations, most notably when limited training data are involved. In addition, QGs showed more consistent results across all scenarios, which suggests that they are less affected by the selection of training components than CNNs.

Introduction

The significance of employing computational methods in decision-making has grown in various scientific and technological disciplines over the past few years¹⁻³. There has been a significant increase in interest in machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) methodologies in the area of pattern recognition and classification. ML and DL algorithms facilitate the processing, analysis, and annotation of various data types⁴⁻⁶. Examples of such data include geological or physiological time series, text data sourced from the internet or books, and medical or satellite images. Machine learning techniques are being used to tackle a broad range of challenges, including supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning issues⁷⁻⁹.

Applying computational tools to tackle decision-making difficulties offers benefits such as increased speed, enhanced precision, and elevated impartiality, characteristics that are more restricted when executed by a human¹⁰⁻¹². Although different ML/DL algorithms for classification employ diverse operations, they all require obtaining strong features that effectively distinguish between the groups to be classified; therefore, the search for useful features remains a field open for further research¹³⁻¹⁵. Reliable features can significantly improve various applications, such as sound and emotion recognition, remote sensing, object detection, and the diagnosis of various diseases¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

Numerous approaches to image pattern classification have achieved outstanding results^{13, 19-21}. The most frequently used image classification methods include support vector machines, k-nearest neighbors, random forests, decision trees, neural networks, and complex networks (CNs)²²⁻²⁶. A range of models with reliable performance has been developed over time. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have notably shown unmatched performance in image classification, as reviewed in¹³. Deep learning models like CNNs are widely used for processing and analyzing visual data, and they have been particularly effective in tasks such as image recognition and segmentation²⁷.

In contrast, the use of CNNs in practical applications is limited by the lack of large-scale datasets and sufficient computing power, which is caused by the high demands for training data and processing time imposed by these algorithms²⁸⁻³³. CNNs are highly dependent on the selection of parameters, including the number of layers, neurons, training epochs, and activation

functions, and no standardized guidelines are available to set these parameters. Most suggested frameworks rely on trial and error and are frequently guided by personal experience to adjust these parameters²⁷. Recent research has demonstrated that specific robust CNN architectures can be susceptible to vulnerabilities when presented with adversarial examples - modified data samples designed to maximize the likelihood of misclassification by the classifier model, highlighting its limitations^{34,35}. There remains a need to introduce new techniques capable of extracting robust characteristics and classifying image patterns to facilitate innovation and progress in both technological and scientific applications^{36,37}.

Researchers have investigated alternative approaches to extract key features from images to improve classification accuracy. Approaches derived from complex network theory have yielded promising results, as observed in many studies^{38,39}. A complex network can be viewed as a collection of N interconnected nodes joined by M edges. Each edge denotes an interaction between two nodes, or, in cases where self-loops occur, it represents the interaction of a node with itself⁴⁰⁻⁴². In recent years, various methodologies employing CNs have been developed, enabling the creation of techniques that can analyze diverse types of data by examining the structural characteristics of the CNs linked to this data. The system or structure in question is represented as a network, and its connections are then characterized by considering various topological metrics⁴³⁻⁴⁷.

A method recently developed from the theory of CNs originated the visibility graphs (VGs). The proposed method, which was initially developed for time series analysis, utilizes the concept of visibility among data points to generate graphs that represent input data in a network framework, as demonstrated in references^{39,46}. Several applications of VGs have demonstrated their potential as powerful tools for time series and image classification tasks. However, such computational models can be extremely time-consuming^{23,48,49}. While the number of nodes in the networks produced by VGs equals the number of data points, the analysis of high-dimensional data becomes impractical. A 512×512 image, which has 262,144 pixels, would be linked to a network with 262,144 nodes, leading to adjacency matrices with $262,144 \times 262,144$ entries³⁸. A substantial number of nodes greatly enhances the processing time for feature computation, thereby restricting the practicality of the proposed method to extensive datasets.

In contrast, a new method based on the concept of time series distribution quantiles has generated computational models called quantile graphs (QGs). The core concept of mapping a time series to a QG involves dividing the time series amplitude distribution into Q quantiles. Following this, each quantile is depicted as a node within a network, with $N = Q$ nodes linked according to the proximity of the corresponding time series points. The process produces a weighted and directed graph with self-loops, containing significantly fewer nodes than the original data points^{50,51}.

Recent studies have used quantile graphs to assess the effects of specific brain disorders, such as epilepsy and Alzheimer disease, as well as the impact of aging on heart rate. These investigations underscored the reliability of QGs for the identification of changes in normal biological processes from physiological time series⁵²⁻⁵⁴. In these studies, QGs were compared to five commonly used nonlinear time-series analysis techniques. The application uses EEG signals from patients with severe Alzheimer's disease and healthy individuals. The results indicated that QGs demonstrated enhanced classification accuracy and lower computational expenses compared to the alternative approaches⁵⁵. Time-series analysis is effective for QGs, but it has not been used for the analysis of two-dimensional data, such as images.

This study suggests an expansion of the QGs method for characterizing and categorizing diverse image types. QGs will be developed from grayscale images, which will then be utilized for feature extraction purposes, given that the produced graphs can be characterized by numerous topological metrics. Consequently, the proposed methodology aims to provide a supplementary approach that complements the established techniques in the field of ML/DL applications in computer vision, specifically, in the feature extraction process. The computational implementation of the QGs mapping for images was conducted using Python and has been made publicly available through a repository⁵⁶.

Convolutional neural networks

The established CNNs were used as a reference point for image classification tasks, and their performance served as a basis for comparison with the introduced QGs. Deep learning algorithms known as CNNs are specifically designed to handle image processing tasks and have proven highly effective in identifying intricate patterns and complex structures. The core concept of a CNN is extracting features from the input image via a convolution operation using kernel filters. These filters are weighted masks that are specifically designed to accentuate visual features, such as corners and textures^{57,58}. The features gained in this process are then input to the neurons and layers of the CNN. These features are used in conjunction with particular activation functions to train the network and subsequently for classification purposes²⁷. The operation of a convolution is depicted in Figure 1, which demonstrates feature extraction using a kernel and an input image. From left to right, the sequence depicts the original image, the image with fixed zero boundaries, the kernel mask, and the resulting feature matrix⁵⁹. The CNNs in this study were implemented with *keras* programming interface, and the implementation process can be accessed at⁵⁶.

Quantile graphs in higher dimensions

QGs were introduced to map a time series $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_L\}$ of length L to a directed weighted graph with $Q \approx 2 \times \sqrt[3]{L}$ nodes⁵¹. Each node specifically stores a particular quantile of the time series values. The weight of the arc connecting nodes

Figure 1. A visual representation of a CNN procedure to extract features from an input image²⁷.

n_i and n_j is determined by the frequency with which a time point x_t in q_i is succeeded by a time point x_{t+r} in q_j , where r represents the temporal distance between two time points, with i and j each ranging from 1 to Q , and t ranging from 1 to $T - r$. The parameter r can be adjusted freely over a given time series length. The accuracy of the mapping, in terms of the graphs' ability to represent time series characteristics, does not rely on the time series being stationary or of a particular length.

We now extend the concept of QGs to higher-dimensional objects such as images. To simplify the analysis, we begin by examining a black-and-white image represented as matrix \mathbf{A} . Mathematically, \mathbf{A} is described by a matrix of size $L_1 \times L_2$. The product of L_1 and L_2 represents the total number of pixels in the image, which can be divided into quantiles using \mathbf{A}_{ij} . We maintain the relationship between the number of data points and the number of quantiles by letting $Q \approx 2 \times \sqrt[3]{L_1 L_2}$.

To map spatial proximity to connectivity, we use a Moore neighborhood with radius r (Fig. 2). Figure 2 illustrates the identification of two different pixels' neighbors using the Moore neighborhood with $r = 1$ and $r = 2$. Note that due to the effect of borders, not all pixels in the image have the same number of neighbors. For example, setting $r = 1$, pixel \mathbf{A}_{11} has 3 adjacent pixels, which correspond to \mathbf{A}_{12} , \mathbf{A}_{21} and \mathbf{A}_{22} . A non-border pixel has 8 neighbors, e.g., pixel \mathbf{A}_{34} is identified as a neighbor of \mathbf{A}_{23} , \mathbf{A}_{24} , \mathbf{A}_{25} , \mathbf{A}_{33} , \mathbf{A}_{35} , \mathbf{A}_{43} , \mathbf{A}_{44} , and \mathbf{A}_{45} , when $r = 1$ is considered. In the resulting network, an undirected arc emerges between the nodes representing the pixels identified as neighbors. Given a value of r , this process of identifying adjacent pixels of a main central pixel is repeated until each pixel is considered as the main one precisely once. This iterative procedure ensures a comprehensive coverage of the entire image in such a way that the spatial relationships and structural arrangements of the pixels are mapped into the QGs topological structure. The proposed method generates undirected and weighted QGs. Varying the r value leads to networks with distinct topologies, and this parameter can be adjusted freely within the boundaries of an image.

The proposed technique is depicted in Figure 3 and entails transforming a 6×6 grayscale image with pixel values ranging from 1 to 100 into QGs with $N = 7$ nodes for both $r = 1$ and $r = 2$ cases. Smaller pixel values are directly linked to lower quantile numbers, where they correlate with darker tones in the original image. In comparison, higher pixel values are linked to higher quantile numbers and indicate more vibrant colors in the input image. Once the pixels are linked to the nodes of the corresponding network, the connections can then be calculated.

For illustration, consider the first pixel shown in Figure 3b, which displays the quantile values at each pixel location. Setting r to 1 and focusing on the first pixel \mathbf{A}_{11} , which corresponds to node n_5 , it becomes clear that its adjacent pixels are \mathbf{A}_{12} , \mathbf{A}_{21} , and \mathbf{A}_{22} , which are linked to nodes n_2 , n_5 and n_6 . In this step, a connection is established between the nodes n_5 and n_2 , between n_5 and itself, and between nodes n_5 and n_6 . In the resulting network (Fig. 3c), it can be seen that the arc connecting nodes n_5 and n_6 has a weight equal to 3, since these nodes were identified as neighbors 3 times within the image, i.e., pixels \mathbf{A}_{11} and \mathbf{A}_{22} , pixels \mathbf{A}_{21} and \mathbf{A}_{22} , and pixels \mathbf{A}_{46} and \mathbf{A}_{36} . Setting r to 2, it can be seen that the weight of the arc connecting nodes n_5 and n_6 is equal to 4 (Fig. 3d), since quantiles q_5 and q_6 are identified 4 times as neighbors in the image, i.e., pixels \mathbf{A}_{16} and \mathbf{A}_{36} , pixels \mathbf{A}_{21} and \mathbf{A}_{43} , pixels \mathbf{A}_{46} and \mathbf{A}_{44} , and pixels \mathbf{A}_{65} and \mathbf{A}_{44} . After processing, the weights of the edges are correlated with the spatial arrangement of the original image's pixel values.

Each QG is linked to a weighted adjacency matrix, denoted as W , which can be characterized using a range of topological metrics. These metrics provide a representation of the mapped image within a network structure and offer benefits for image processing and classification. Similar to a one-dimensional method, two-dimensional QG's can effectively represent two-dimensional data types, such as images, without considering their distribution, scale, or scope.

Figure 2. Identification of neighboring pixels of a pixel using the Moore neighborhood for a given radius r in a 6×6 input image. The primary and adjacent pixels are represented by dark and light gray squares, respectively.

Methods

Topological measures

In graph analysis, local and global topological metrics are essential for numerous investigations, including the representation, characterization, and categorization of a network's attributes. Similar to many previous studies on complex networks, we modeled the relevant structures (such as images) as networks and subsequently analyzed the informative attributes identified by topological measures as described in^{41,44}. For each resulting graph in this context, four key topological measures were computed: the clustering coefficient, Laplacian Estrada index, graph energy, and jump length. These particular measures were chosen because they can effectively extract key information from weighted adjacency matrices and are computationally efficient^{50,52–55,60,61}.

The results from calculating the topological measures are utilized as feature inputs for an XGBoost classifier. XGBoost is a robust machine learning model, primarily used for supervised learning tasks, such as classification and regression, and is noted for its high precision and speed when processing a large number of features⁶². In all simulations, the training time was minimized using the *SelectKBest* function from *sklearn* to perform feature selection, which involved selecting $K = 100$ features and reducing the total number of features obtained to 100.

Clustering coefficient Network clustering is characterized by nodes that tend to group together in “triangles”, which are clusters of three interconnected nodes. The formation of connected neighborhoods in a network can be quantified using the clustering coefficient⁶³. In the context of a weighted directed graph and node n_i , the clustering coefficient C_i is defined as the ratio between all weighted directed triangles formed by n_i and the total potential triangles n_i could create. The clustering coefficient C_i for node n_i in a weighted undirected adjacency matrix W can be computed as:

$$C_i = \frac{\left(\overline{W}^{\frac{1}{3}}\right)^3}{d_i(d_i - 1)}, \quad (1)$$

69	16	11	9	19	55
75	83	97	40	27	15
46	54	1	26	15	86
9	99	78	81	14	63
23	8	82	44	87	36
92	45	87	92	58	52

(a) Grayscale input image.

5	2	1	1	2	5
5	6	7	3	3	2
4	4	1	3	2	6
1	7	6	6	2	5
3	1	6	4	7	3
7	4	7	7	5	4

(b) Identification of the quantiles.

(c) Resulting graph for $r = 1$.

(d) Resulting graph for $r = 2$.

Figure 3. Illustration of the proposed technique for transforming a 6×6 grayscale image into QGs with seven nodes, in cases where the radius r is either one or two.

for $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$. The normalized weighted adjacency matrix, \overline{W} , is obtained by dividing all elements in W by its maximum value, and the total number of edges connecting node n_i is quantified by d_i . The global average clustering coefficient of a network is obtained by calculating the following formula:

$$\mathcal{C} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N C_i. \quad (2)$$

Laplacian Estrada index The Laplacian matrix for a given matrix W is obtained by subtracting W from a diagonal matrix D , in which each diagonal entry corresponds to the degree of the associated node^{54,64,65}. The Laplacian Estrada index \mathcal{L} can be calculated using the given eigenvalues of the Laplacian matrix, μ_i for each of the $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ values (Eq. 3).

$$\mathcal{L} = \sum_{i=1}^N e^{\mu_i} \quad (3)$$

Graph energy In spectral analysis of complex networks, eigenvalues are indispensable measures representing the graph's spectra. Given an $N \times N$ adjacency matrix that yields N eigenvalues, these measures can be associated with the paths of possible random walks performed over the graph, providing metrics referent to the graph's structure^{66,67}. Given the set of eigenvalues, λ_i for $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, the graph energy \mathcal{E} can be calculated as the sum of their absolute values⁶⁸:

$$\mathcal{E} = \sum_{i=1}^N |\lambda_i| \quad (4)$$

Jump length The Markov transition matrix P can be derived from adjacency matrix W , where each element $p_{i,j}$ signifies the likelihood of transitioning from quantile q_i to q_j . According to mathematical formulation⁵⁰, the transition probability is

computed as follows:

$$p_{i,j} = \frac{w_{i,j}}{\sum_{j=1}^N w_{i,j}}. \quad (5)$$

Following normalization, each $p_{i,j}$ represents the probability of moving from node n_i to node n_j . As a result, it is possible to perform a random walk on the graph, calculating the average over all jumps of length $|i - j|$. The mean jump length Δ can be quickly calculated from the transition matrix, such that⁵⁰:

$$\Delta = \frac{1}{N} \text{tr}(HP^{\mathcal{T}}), \quad (6)$$

where H is a $N \times N$ matrix with $h_{i,j} = |i - j|$, $P^{\mathcal{T}}$ is the transpose of P , and tr represents the trace operation.

Data

MNIST-C The standard Modified National Institute of Standards and Technology (MNIST) dataset comprises 70,000 images, with 60,000 images reserved for training and 10,000 images reserved for testing. The initial separation of training and testing components in this dataset facilitates the creation of unbiased comparisons between various classification methods. Each image consists of 28×28 pixels and depicts handwritten digits ranging from 0 to 9. The MNIST dataset has been employed in numerous image processing studies as a standard reference point for machine learning and deep learning methodologies^{69–72}. The MNIST-C dataset is an extension of the original MNIST dataset^{73,74}. The MNIST-C dataset was created by introducing 15 different types of corruption to the 70,000 images sourced from MNIST, resulting in deliberate noise effects and/or distortions to the original numbers’ shapes to increase the difficulty level for predictive models^{75–77}. The MNIST-C dataset examples in Figure 4 feature 15 distinct corruption from the original MNIST dataset, with the “identity” corruption serving as a representation of no corruption. This study utilizes the MNIST-C dataset to evaluate the proposed QGs method against widely recognized CNNs.

Fashion MNIST-C The Fashion MNIST dataset was created as a more demanding alternative to the traditional MNIST dataset of handwritten digits for testing computer vision capabilities. Similar to MNIST, this dataset has the same number of training and test samples and the same image resolution; however, it includes images of various clothing items, resulting in a greater diversity of visual complexity^{78,79}. We obtained the Fashion MNIST-C dataset by merging corruption from the MNIST-C dataset with the Fashion MNIST dataset, as depicted in Figure 5.

Results and discussion

MNIST-C

The images from the MNIST-C dataset were used to map a grayscale image into QGs using the novel approach. Using $Q = 2 \times \sqrt[3]{28 \times 28} \approx 18$ quantiles and $r = 1, \dots, 10$, networks with $N = 18$ nodes were generated for each image. A total of 760 features were calculated for each image, resulting from the product of 4 topological measures, 10 different values of r , and the sum of 18 local measures plus 1 global measure. The transition matrices in Figure 6 were calculated by applying the QG mapping to the images in Figure 4 with a radius of 1. Transitions between quantiles are commonly found near the diagonal, suggesting a connection between nodes, most notably in instances involving corruption such as “brightness”, “identity”, “rotate” or “scale”. Unlike some forms of corruption, like “glass blur”, “fog”, and “motion blur”, these transition characteristics are disrupted, leading to local smoothing in the transition matrices. The results indicate that QGs are able to capture transitions between pixel values and identify changes in the structural properties of the generated networks when image corruptions are introduced.

The accuracy values of the MNIST-C dataset are presented in Table 1, which were calculated using the entire 60,000 element training set. As anticipated, the greatest level of accuracy for both methods was achieved on the “identity” images, which were not subjected to any extra noise beyond the original images. The peak CNN and QG accuracies for the “identity” images were 97.49% and 94.02%, respectively. The methods vary in terms of their worst-case performance metrics. For CNNs, the lowest accuracy recorded was 93.09%, on images that had been corrupted with the “translate” manipulation. In contrast, QGs achieved a minimum accuracy of 55.56% on images that were corrupted with “fog”. The CNN architecture employed in this study was tailored to and fine-tuned for the MNIST dataset; nonetheless, it is apparent that CNNs consistently obtained higher accuracy rates across all instances listed in Table 1. It is noteworthy that QGs showed substantial performance in categorizing images from this dataset, attaining accuracy levels of over 90.00% in numerous cases, implying that this newly proposed technique has the potential to be a practical method for image classification and pattern recognition.

Figure 4. The MNIST-C dataset exemplars which includes the original MNIST dataset, denoted as “identity”, and 15 distinct types of image degradation.

The boxplots in Figure 7 illustrate the accuracy of each technique across 100 simulated runs. For each simulation, the test set remained unchanged at 10,000 elements, while a random selection of 30,000 images was made from the full training set of 60,000 images to assess the classification abilities of CNNs and QGs under training data limitations. For a consistent assessment, the same randomly chosen subset of 30,000 elements was used in each simulation for both methods. The findings depicted in Figure 7 are consistent with those presented in Table 1, showing that the “identity” corruption results in the highest accuracy for both methods, with CNNs performing better than QGs in all instances. Furthermore, “translation” and “fog” persist as the most difficult corruption for CNNs and QGs, respectively. Significantly, the boxplot dispersion and interquartile range indicate that despite CNNs achieving higher overall accuracy, QGs exhibit reduced accuracy variance across simulations, as the blue boxes representing CNNs are broader than the red ones representing QGs in each instance. While CNNs may yield more accurate results, QGs exhibit greater stability and consistency, which implies that the proposed approach is less susceptible to

Figure 5. The Fashion MNIST-C dataset exemplars which includes the original Fashion MNIST data, referred to as “identity”, alongside 15 types of image degradation.

variations in the selection of training data. In comparison with CNNs, the proposed model’s performance is less dependent on particular training samples, thereby underscoring the potential resilience of QGs in classification tasks.

Similarly, Figure 8 displays boxplots showing the accuracy achieved by each technique over 100 simulations using a subset of 10,000 images randomly selected from the MNIST-C training set. As observed in Figure 7, the boxplots in Figure 8 reveal a larger spread and interquartile range for CNNs than for QGs, suggesting that QGs provide more stable and consistent results. Unlike the previous analysis with 30,000 training elements, QGs outperformed CNNs in some cases, including “brightness”, “motion blur”, “scale”, “shear”, and “translate”. This indicates that QGs may offer greater robustness than CNNs when working with limited training data.

Figure 6. Transition matrices generated for an image from the MNIST-C dataset under various forms of corruption, all with a value of $r = 1$.

Fashion MNIST-C

The images from the Fashion MNIST-C dataset were also mapped into QGs using $N = 18$ nodes and $r = 1, \dots, 10$, hence 760 features were calculated for each image. Figure 9 shows the transition matrices obtained for the images displayed in Figure 5 using $r = 1$. In contrast to the results observed for the MNIST-C dataset, the plots in Figure 9 display smoother and less concentrated transitions close to the diagonal, even in the “identity” case. These findings align with the characteristics of the mapped images, as the handwritten digits in MNIST-C exhibit more distinct and defined transitions between pixel colors, while the clothing items in Fashion MNIST-C present a greater variety of shapes and more gradual transitions between pixel colors. Once again, corruptions like “rotate” or “translate” result in minimal visible changes in the transition matrices, whereas corruptions like “fog”, “glass blur”, or “shot noise” appear to disrupt the visual patterns, thereby altering the properties of the

Table 1. The accuracy of CNNs and QGs on the MNIST-C dataset, using the entire 60,000-element training sample.

Corruption	CNNs	QGs
Brightness	0.9546	0.9395
Canny edges	0.9711	0.9085
Dotted line	0.9628	0.8924
Fog	0.9535	0.5556
Glass blur	0.9433	0.8883
Identity	0.9749	0.9402
Impulse noise	0.9590	0.8645
Motion blur	0.9593	0.9358
Rotate	0.9509	0.9047
Scale	0.9712	0.9299
Shear	0.9610	0.9278
Shot noise	0.9642	0.9299
Spatter	0.9625	0.7957
Stripe	0.9670	0.9193
Translate	0.9309	0.8944
Zigzag	0.9590	0.8700

Figure 7. A comparison of the accuracy of CNNs and QGs for the MNIST-C dataset using a training sample comprising 30,000 elements, which was selected randomly across 100 simulations.

generated networks.

Table 2 shows the values of accuracy obtained for the Fashion MNIST-C dataset when the full training set (60,000 elements) was used. As expected, given the increased complexity in the input images compared to the images from MNIST-C, both techniques performed better on the MNIST-C dataset than on Fashion MNIST-C. Again, the highest accuracy for both methods was achieved on the “identity” images, with CNNs and QGs reaching peak accuracies of 83.45% and 86.58%, respectively. Consistent with the results for MNIST-C, the lowest accuracy for CNNs was observed with “translate” corruption (75.56%), while QGs had the lowest accuracy with “fog” corruption (67.53%). With the single exception, QGs consistently outperformed CNNs in classifying images from Fashion MNIST-C. The CNN architecture used in this study was specifically designed to classify handwritten digits in the MNIST dataset; however, it has limitations when applied to clothing items from Fashion

Figure 8. Comparison between the accuracy of CNNs and QGs for the MNIST-C dataset, using a training sample with 10,000 elements randomly selected over 100 simulations.

MNIST. These findings demonstrate that CNNs are highly sensitive to parameter selection and network architecture, which reduces their reliability for general application across different datasets.

Table 2. Comparison between the accuracy of CNNs and QGs for the Fashion MNIST-C dataset, using the whole training sample with 60,000 elements.

Corruption	CNNs	QGs
Brightness	0.8051	0.8586
Canny edges	0.8153	0.8162
Dotted line	0.8169	0.8475
Fog	0.7782	0.6753
Glass blur	0.7951	0.8301
Identity	0.8345	0.8658
Impulse noise	0.7867	0.8273
Motion blur	0.7886	0.8164
Rotate	0.7903	0.8358
Scale	0.8326	0.8524
Shear	0.7769	0.8358
Shot noise	0.7939	0.8178
Spatter	0.7987	0.8220
Stripe	0.8260	0.8631
Translate	0.7556	0.8292
Zigzag	0.8063	0.8359

The boxplots in Figure 10 were generated from 100 simulations, with each simulation involving a random selection of 30,000 images from the Fashion MNIST-C training set. In contrast to the MNIST-C analysis, QGs outperformed CNNs across all cases, with the medians of the red boxes being higher than those of the blue boxes, except in the “fog” case. Both techniques achieved their highest accuracy involving the “identity” corruption, whereas the lowest accuracy was observed in “fog” and

Figure 9. Examples of transition matrices generated for an image from the Fashion MNIST-C dataset, using different forms of corruption and $r = 1$.

“translate” cases for QGs and CNNs, respectively. In addition, QGs exhibit lower variance and greater consistency.

Figure 8 illustrates boxplots representing the accuracy of each method across 100 simulations; the images used here are a randomly chosen subset of 10,000 from the MNIST-C training set. Figure 8 boxplots show a larger spread and interquartile range than those in Figure 7, indicating that QGs produce more stable and consistent results than CNNs. QGs surpass CNNs in all instances. This result suggests that QGs provide improved stability compared to CNNs in scenarios with restricted training data availability.

Figure 10. Comparison between the accuracy of CNNs and QGs for the Fashion MNIST-C dataset, using a training sample with 30,000 elements randomly selected over 100 simulations.

Figure 11. Comparison between the accuracy of CNNs and QGs for the Fashion MNIST-C dataset, using a training sample consisting of 10,000 elements, randomly selected across 100 simulations.

Conclusions

In this study, we propose an extension of quantile graphs, which have been primarily used for mapping time series into complex networks, to transform grayscale images. We extracted QGs from two benchmark datasets (MNIST and Fashion MNIST)

and then employed topological measures as features to classify the images. Our results were compared with those achieved by convolutional neural networks, which are renowned for their superior performance in computer vision tasks. Our results indicate that CNNs often record higher accuracy; however, the newly introduced QGs exhibit superior accuracy in certain instances, notably in settings with restricted training data. In every scenario, QGs exhibit greater consistency, which suggests that they are less susceptible to selection of training components than CNNs. The results indicate that the proposed QGs in higher-dimensional spaces provide a robust method for feature extraction from grayscale images, providing an alternative method for image analysis and classification. Future research will involve expanding the proposed method to include RGB colored images and 3D volumetric images, achieved through minor adjustments to our existing approach.

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Data availability

The datasets analyzed during the current study are freely available for download in the GitHub and Zenodo repositories through <https://github.com/zalandoresearch/fashion-mnist/tree/master/data> and <https://zenodo.org/records/3239543>, respectively.

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